

Characteristics of Psychological Preparation of Young Athletes Working in Sports Clubs for Upcoming Competitions

Suyarov Khurshid Bakhriddinovich ¹, Bakhriddinov is the son of Ruslan Khurshid ²

¹ Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, "Physical culture" department, associate professor

² Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, "Physical culture" department, student

Abstract:

It is known that many of our trainers do not work on psychology, even though they perform technical, tactical and strength exercises for various reasons. The real reason for this is that most of our trainers, although they have more or less knowledge of other subjects, have not mastered the science of psychology well. That is why they should get help from outside or work with a specialist. However, this issue is often never put on the agenda or studied.

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INTRODUCTION

According to experts, insufficient psychological preparation can cause more serious negative consequences and decrease performance than physical, technical and tactical preparation. It is known that despite very good physical, technical and tactical training, many athletes and even teams can achieve unsuccessful results. In recent years, the number of people involved in sports psychology has increased significantly.

3 important reasons for leaving little time for psychological skills are:

1. Lack of knowledge: Most coaches do not know how to teach and apply psychological skills to athletes.

2. Misconceptions about psychological skills: It is difficult to believe that psychological skills are innate.

3. Lack of time: insufficient training time and equipment. As a result, many coaches today do not use enough psychological training. Many coaches and team managers see athletes as physical, technical and tactical individuals. On the other hand, they try to deal with psychological preparation verbally. However, taking into account the positive effect of psychological preparation on performance, it is necessary to make both coaches and athletes more aware.

In today's world, it is gradually being understood that sports performance does not consist only of physical, tactical and technical elements. Practices have shown that the psychological aspect of sports is an important factor that complements other elements (physical, tactical and technical). It comes not only with physical, technical and tactical preparation, but also with psychological preparation and regulation of social life. Performances in sports are a whole, and it is necessary to achieve harmony within the framework of integrity. Experts say that the highest performance is a combination of physical and mental skills, and psychological skills are as important to success as physical skills. Psychological skills can be taught just like physical skills. For this, the training of psychological skills should be programmed and applied regularly and systematically, just like physical education. Psychological skills training includes curricula and programs to develop skills such as relaxation, staying motivated, stress management, goal setting, visualization, self-confidence, attention and concentration management, and thought management. The fact that most coaches do not pay attention to the psychological aspect of the athlete's activity is the reason for their failure.

There are typological differences in the implementation of psychological training. Athletes with a strong nervous system feel less need for special individualization of psychological training under normal conditions than athletes with a weaker nervous system. The nervous system is at its peak performance when the "Junk Athlete" performs a very large amount of work in chunks. Inert athletes should have a detailed plan of their actions in the competition, and this plan should be very well thought out, it includes specific methods and tools prepared tactically for any difficult situation. Active athletes do not feel the need for such detailed planning, so tasks of a more general form are set before them. Too much work and too much training exhausts active athletes, kills interest, wastes energy, and causes a loss of initiative. It is known that will is a unique form of human activity, and it is very important for such functions as setting life goals and correct organization of behavior. Will is a set of voluntary actions that arise under the influence of human needs and are clearly visible in the course of an activity. Although there are many scientific concepts and approaches to the problem of volitional qualities, there is still no single definition that explains it. That is why there are many conflicting views on the question of human willpower and its formation. There are many scientific concepts on the issue of will and volitional qualities, in which you can find unique views on the problem.

Mental phenomena fall into 3 interrelated groups, mental processes, mental characteristics of the individual, and mental states. The last of these (mental state) has different durations and images. As a result of psychological preparation, a state of mental preparation for participation in a sports competition is created. It is characterized by the need to activate mental processes for competitive fighting. The mental preparation of a young athlete is of great importance in sports activities, and it remains one of the main conditions for success. Confidence of the athlete in his own strength, desire to fight sports, mobilize all his strength and achieve victory. Optimal tolerance of emotional arousal. Being able to deal with his behavior through sports wrestling.

The system of psychological preparation for the competition includes a number of tasks, and in the process of solving these tasks, the athlete's mental preparation for the competition is formed. The system of psychological preparation of the athlete for the competition includes the following links:

gathering information about the conditions of the competition, assessing the state of the athlete's training before the competition, and self-evaluation. Purposes and tasks of participation in the competition. Activating the motives of participation in the competition. Planning experiments of mental activity, forming a sense of confidence in the athlete to realize his potential.

Ability to activate maximum voluntary effort and demonstrate it in competitive conditions. Forming an optimal emotional state. Mastering methods of managing mental states and self-control in competitive conditions.

The above links are connected with each other, if one of the links becomes loose, the whole system may fail. During preparation for the competition, information about the conditions of the competition, the opponent, the place of the competition and the participants is very important. Knowledge about one's opponent allows to develop specific measures for preparing for the competition, the lack of information about the opponent causes anxiety in the athlete. The form of information delivery is of great importance in the process of psychological training.

The same message can be announced in such a way that it can create a positive attitude or attitude towards the fight in the upcoming competition. A highly trained state (in a sports uniform) allows the athlete to show better physical, technical and tactical information in his activities.

In sports practice, there are a number of objective methods for evaluating the trained state of an athlete, but these methods cannot be complete without relying on self-assessment (for example, if, according to all objective data, an athlete is well trained, but if he subjectively feels that he has not reached the state of sports form, which prevents him from successfully participating in the competition. An athlete or a team participating in a competition should have a clear and understandable task. The nature of the competition task and the athlete's attitude to it determine his emotional experiences with a certain power. That is why the athlete should reveal the importance and essence of the tasks he has set for himself. The goal of the competition is that for the athlete, the competition should become his belief.

The importance of the formation of socially important motives in the psychological training of athletes, especially in responsibility competitions, is great. Planning future sports activities is carried out in the form of movement imaginations subject to the ideomotor law. Confidence is a prerequisite for athletes to realize their potential. Lack of trust is the opposite. The athlete's confidence in his ability is the result of his physical, technical and tactical preparation.

In conclusion, the teacher should record the results and literature sources about the characteristics of emotional experiences during the competition and their impact on the athlete's actions.

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